

OpenFlow Support for the Next Generation TelcoEdgeCloud with TeraFlowSDN

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Abstract—As data center environments evolve to a unified TelcoEdgeCloud, scalable and adaptable SDN solutions are required to guarantee dynamic and flexible intra-DC connectivity. SYLVA is a reference implementation of a cloud software framework which is able to address the technical challenges of the TelcoEdgeCloud industry. This paper presents the architectural design involving SYLVA and TeraFlowSDN, an open-source, cloud-native SDN controller, to support intra-DC connectivity. The work concludes with an experimental validation of the proposed approach.

Index Terms—OpenFlow, SDN, Telco Edge Cloud

I. INTRODUCTION

As cloud and edge computing environments evolve, succeeding in a dynamic intra-data center connectivity has become a critical challenge. SYLVA, an open-source cloud software framework founded by the linux foundation was developed to address complex requirements of TelecoCloud and Edge industry. On the other hand, network automation and management remain a concern in ensuring intra-DC connectivity [1]. ETSI TeraFlowSDN is an open-source system supporting cloud-native SDN controller functionality to manage large-scale network flows [2]. TeraFlowSDN is built on microservices that operate autonomously by using custom open Google Remote Procedure Call (gRPC) interface to communicate with one another. This approach provides important benefits including flexibility alongside scalability, and resilience which remain major requirements for cloud-scale systems. Currently, TeraFlowSDN is used for layer-3 network applications and secure traffic management systems [3] [4]. To address such challenges, we propose an architectural design that integrates SYLVA with TeraFlowSDN.

Our approach aims to improve TeraFlowSDN capabilities by integrating OpenFlow, a standard protocol for network control and management that dynamically manages data flows. Through OpenFlow protocol, networks vendors are able to manage flows without revealing the underlying switching

mechanisms. OpenFlow-based SDN is increasingly deployed in various networking devices and software facilitating development for intra/inter data center connectivity [5]. Our work specifically targets network monitoring and control app development by extending OpenFlow support to the Ryu SDN controller which maintains a simple and well-defined API. The growing usage of cloud services requires high system availability and high levels of reliability to maintain service quality failures in cloud infrastructure. This leads to both reduced service availability and losses along with data integrity problems. To cope with these risks, service providers respond to these threats by deploying their services across multiple geographically distributed data centers. However, these data centers experience an increase in failure rates during scaling operations [6]. To address these challenges and improve network resilience, we design a L3VPN connectivity service based on OpenFlow rules using TeraFlowSDN with the aim to enable dynamic network configuration and reduce errors in service operations.

II. ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1 shows the proposed architecture for dynamic deployment of intra-DC L3VPN connectivity service including SYLVA, TeraFlowSDN, Ryu, and Mininet. SYLVA is responsible for managing resources and services in cloud and edge data centers [1]. TeraFlowSDN microservice-based components are described. *Web-based User Interface (WebUI)* uses gRPC interfaces to inspect network state, as well as to issue operational requests to the TeraFlowSDN components.

Service component manages connectivity services, such as L3VPNs, ensuring end-to-end network provisioning. Given the variety of service types, a Handler API is implemented that allows network operators to integrate custom service types and fine-tune their behavior. *PathComp* is responsible for computing the optimal paths between endpoints based on network topology and link status. *Device* component interacts with the network devices using the South-Bound Interfaces (SBIs) implemented as pluggable drivers. A Driver Application Programming Interface (API) has been defined to facilitate the addition of new network protocols and data models. We deployed the Ryu Driver for communications with Ryu devices through OpenFlow-based REST requests. *Context* is responsible for storing network configuration (e.g., topologies, devices, links, services) managed by the TeraFlowSDN in a No-SQL

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Fig. 1. OpenFlow Support with TeraFlowSDN Architecture

database to optimize concurrent access. It provides publish-subscribe mechanisms over gRPC to broadcast change events to other TeraFlowSDN OS components. *NBI* component serves as the interface for internal gRPC and protocol buffers towards external Representational State Transfer (REST)-like requests.

The TeraFlowSDN components are implemented as microservices in Python and interact with each other. They are deployed on top of a Kubernetes-based environment and rely on well-defined gRPC-based messages and services for their internal communications. On the other hand, Ryu is built as a modular, component-based framework in which every module handles different aspects of an SDN controller. In our work, we used several key components. *Ryu ofctl_rest* provides REST API communication with OpenFlow switches. It allows management of switches by sending flow rules, retrieving stats and managing network configurations via HTTP requests *Link Observation* uses Link Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP) and helps in detecting the network topology by identifying links between switches. *GUI topology* launches the Ryu GUI-based topology viewer for visualization of the network topology displaying switches links and hosts. When instantiating Ryu, the commands does not include the central application manager and OpenFlow controller which are explicitly inherited to the application. The central management module manages loading Ryu applications. On the other hand, the OpenFlow controller handles connections to switches, and generates route events to entities like Ryu applications.

The OpenFlow Controller has the following components: a) *ryu.controller.controller*, which handles connections to OpenFlow switches and routing incoming messages; b) *ryu.controller.ofp_event* that contains the definitions of OpenFlow events such as packet-in, port status, etc. that are used to trigger application-specific logic; c) *ryu.controller.handler*, which provides the decorators and infrastructure for registering event handlers within Ryu applications; d) *ryu.controller.ofp_handler* that implements the logic for parsing and processing OpenFlow messages received from

the switches; e) *ryu.controller.dpset*, which manages the set of connected datapaths (switches) and their states.

Finally, Mininet serves as a lightweight network emulator helping in the creation of virtual networks for SDN research and testing. Mininet hosts runs on a full Linux network stack. It supports OpenFlow, so it works with OpenFlow-Controllers like Ryu. One of the important features of Mininet is that it provides Python API for scripting complex network topologies, and it comes with a Command Line Interface (CLI) for network management. This architecture provides a scalable approach for managing L3-VPN connectivity services using TeraFlowSDN, Ryu, SYLVA and Mininet. Using TeraFlowSDN’s gRPC-based communication along with Kubernetes deployment helps in network automation.

Fig. 2. Device Onboarding Workflow

III. ESTABLISHING DYNAMIC INTRA-DATA CENTER CONNECTIVITY

In this section, we present the workflows that enable the dynamic deployment and management of intra-data center connectivity within TeraFlowSDN. This work is represented in the workflows depicted in Fig. 2 and Fig.3

Fig. 3. Service Provisioning Workflow

a) *Device Onboarding Workflow*: Fig. 2 shows the onboarding process through TeraFlowSDN. Initially, a user requests a new device in the TeraFlowSDN operating system for example, through the WebUI. Once the *WebUI* receives the request it triggers the *Device* Component, which is responsible for handling network devices. The *Device* component instantiates *Ryu Driver* establishing a connection to *Ryu* controller to fetch the topology. The *Ryu* controller responds with the information on detected devices, flows, and links detected, forwarding this information back to the driver. Finally, the *Device* component returns the topology retrieved to the *WebUI* to complete the process. Hence, the topology is on-boarded, and the network elements can be managed through TeraFlowSDN ecosystem.

b) *Service Provisioning Workflow*: Fig. 3 represents the service provisioning workflow through TeraFlowSDN, showing how a service is requested by SYLVA and processed through various components within TeraFlowSDN reaching *Ryu* Controller. First, *SYLVA* initiates a service request through *NBI* that forwards the request to the *Service* Component. Afterwards, the *Service* component requests the *PathComp* to compute the optimal path. The *PathComp* calculates the path and responds to the *Service* Component with the calculated path. Upon receiving the path details, the *Service Handler* to prepare the device configurations and send them to the *Driver*. The *Driver* using its *Ryu Driver* sends Rest API requests such as *set/get/delete/update* to *Ryu* for configuration. Lastly, *Ryu* processes these requests by configuring *Open vSwitches* and responds by notifying that the changes were applied. Once everything is successfully configured, the *NBI* replies to *SYLVA* that the service was created.

Fig. 4. TeraFlowSDN:Onboarding

IV. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The *Kubernetes* environment is deployed at *CTTC* premises in *ADRENALINE* Testbed [7]. *Kubernetes* is a container orchestrator that provides management capabilities and can operate geographically in distributed infrastructures [8] [4]. The data obtained through the interaction of TeraFlowSDN's microservices, the *RYU* controller, and *Mininet* are outlined to demonstrate the successful on-boarding process and service creation between hosts connected to *Open vSwitches*. Fig. 4 shows the successful on-boarded topology on the TeraFlowSDN WebUI. When a user uploads a JSON descriptor file, the onboarding workflow described above is initiated resulting in the topology discovery. Fig. 5 confirms that the service creation process on TeraFlowSDN's WebUI was successful. Two services were established on discovered topology (Fig. 4): the first connected *Host 1* to *Host 3* by linking *Open vSwitch 2* to *Open vSwitch 5* via *Open vSwitch 1* after applying the necessary *OpenFlow* rules. Similarly, the second service connected *Host 2* to *Host 4*, establishing a path from *Open vSwitch 2* to *Open vSwitch 5* through *Open vSwitch 1*.

Services

+ Add New Service

2 services found in context *admin*

UUID	Name	Type	End points	Status
1dd09bbe-b2d1-5976-b23c-5a3c49ae6f36	h1-to-h3-l3svc	L3NM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> int / Device: h1 int / Device: h3 	ACTIVE
353f5c32-159f-5664-98a7-2589bfe56540	h2-to-h4-l3svc	L3NM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> int / Device: h2 int / Device: h4 	ACTIVE

Fig. 5. TeraFlowSDN:Services created

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
0.024177593	10.1.29.179	10.1.7.197	HTTP	236	GET /v1.0/topology/switches HTTP/1.1
0.028285694	10.1.7.197	10.1.29.179	HTTP/JSON	1863	HTTP/1.1 200 OK, JSON (application/json)
0.036379143	10.1.29.179	10.1.7.197	HTTP	233	GET /v1.0/topology/links HTTP/1.1
0.366779842	127.0.0.1	127.0.0.1	OpenFlow	168	Type: OFPT_PACKET_OUT
0.083282723	10.1.7.197	10.1.29.137	HTTP/JSON	5588	POST /restconf/data/ietf-l3vpn-svc:l3vpn-svc/vpn-services HTTP/1.1
0.084332226	10.1.29.137	10.1.29.136	HTTP/JSON	5807	POST /restconf/data/ietf-l3vpn-svc:l3vpn-svc/vpn-services HTTP/1.1
0.209234013	127.0.0.1	127.0.0.1	HTTP	771	HTTP/1.1 200 OK (text/plain)
0.618181582	10.1.7.197	10.1.29.166	HTTP	177	GET /login HTTP/1.1
0.952729595	10.1.29.179	10.1.7.197	HTTP/JSON	286	POST /stats/flowentry/add HTTP/1.1, JSON (application/json)
0.952121736	127.0.0.1	127.0.0.1	OpenFlow	168	Type: OFPT_PACKET_OUT
0.953014575	127.0.0.1	127.0.0.1	OpenFlow	170	Type: OFPT_PACKET_IN

Fig. 6. HTTP/OpenFlow Wireshark Captures

Time	Source	Destination	Protocol	Length	Info
0.000005468	10.0.0.1	10.0.0.3	ICMP	100	Echo (ping) request
0.000041437	10.0.0.3	10.0.0.1	ICMP	100	Echo (ping) reply

Fig. 7. L3 host connectivity established

The experimental validation has been carried out using Wireshark to analyse sent/received data packets. Fig. 6 is a Wireshark capture showing network traffic related to OpenFlow-SDN based environment. The capture shows that the communication between network components is the OpenFlow protocol. Messages such as OFPT_FLOW_MOD, OFPT_PACKET_IN, and OFPT_PACKET_OUT indicates the interaction between the RYU controller and the Open vSwitches. On the other hand the HTTP/JSON packets specifically POST, shows that the flow rules are being installed by interaction of TeraFlowSDN and Ryu’s REST API to modify flow tables. On the other hand the figure also shows the service request through the NBI of TeraFlowSDN using the IETF L3VPN. Fig. 7 is Wireshark capture showing ICMP (Internet Control Message Protocol) traffic. Its shows the ping (echo request and reply) messages, exchanged between IP addresses. The capture shows ICMP echo requests and replies between 10.0.0.1 (HOST 1) and 10.0.0.3 (HOST3). The successful exchange of ICMP requests and replies indicates that routing and forwarding OpenFlow rules in the network are working correctly.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presented the design and implementation of L3VPN connectivity service using TeraFlowSDN, Ryu, and Mininet. It demonstrates the integration of an OpenFlow-based SDN controller within a cloud-native SDN environment. Through this work, we successfully on-boarded net-

work devices through Ryu, computed optimal paths, and provisioned services. The results showed that TeraFlowSDN’s microservices along with Ryu’s OpenFlow support facilitate network automation and management, enhancing cloud-network environments. SYLVA plays an important role in managing cloud and edge infrastructures, thus communicating with TeraFlowSDN via the NBI to efficiently request and install services. As future work, we plan to explore SYLVA’s capabilities for data center management and aligning it with TeraFlowSDN to improve cloud orchestration.

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